

Classical Free Particle Physics Contained in $\exp(ipx)$?

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$\exp(ipx)$ is the free particle wavefunction and it is a complex number and so does not correspond to a physical observable or count as in a classical probability such as one used in a coin toss. In traditional quantum mechanics, one multiplies $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx) / \{\sqrt{L}\sqrt{L}\} = 1/L$ to obtain a classical $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length.

$P(x)$ contains less information than $\exp(ipx)$ and we argue that it only corresponds to a certain kind of measurement/experiment, namely one which does not depend on the resolution length \hbar/p . There are physical measurements which exist in the classical world, namely a classical two-slit apparatus, which performs a different kind of measurement, namely a resolution one which requires the use of $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is then treated as a probability, but as a complex number it predicts a complex outcome. To obtain a result which may be measured using a measurement which does not depend on resolution, one applies $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x) = \exp(ipr_1) + \exp(ipr_2)$ where r_1 and r_2 are lengths from each slit to the same point on a screen far away.

One may ask: Why should one use $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ or W^*W ? We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ represents resolution units of length \hbar/p which are repeated. (This we argue follows from special relativity.) If one assumes maximum entropy (consistent with $x=vt$) in each unit, then if one were to ignore the resolution length, \hbar/p , one would have a uniform distribution, i.e. $P(x)dx = dx/L$ in all of space, i.e. consider a quantum particle moving through free space and hitting a target. Thus, even at the $\exp(ipx)$ level, one needs a way to map into a uniform distribution, though this only holds for $L = \hbar/p$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ yields a uniform distribution meaning that no resolution based interaction occurs (i.e. this is not a 2-slit type of measurement).

This then begs the question: What should one do for an infinite potential well. Classically a particle moves according to $x=vt$, interacts and then moves back according to $x = -vt$. $P(x)dx = \text{constant } dx$. The quantum approach on the other hand demonstrates crests and troughs from $\exp(ipx)$ showing that \hbar/p resolution is important in the problem. Nevertheless, one has $x=vt$ within each crest or trough and so unless one may determine the resolution \hbar/p , one cannot see the impact of quantum mechanics and would use $P(x)dx = dx/L$ which shows less information, i.e. ignores the effects of quantum resolution in an interaction with $V(x)$, the potential in a bound problem.

What is a Classical $P(x)$ Measurement

We suggest that there seems to be an issue with the definition of a classical $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for a free particle. We suggest that $P(x)$ depends on a measurement on a particle and that many kinds of measurements are possible, even in the classical world. $P(x)$ is associated with a measurement which is not associated with the resolution \hbar/p of $\exp(ipx)$, we suggest. In other words, a hit occurs in some small dx region, even if it is smaller than \hbar/p .

A 2-slit apparatus is completely classical and may also be considered to be a classical measurement. The problem is that such a measurement gives results which cannot be

described by traditional classical mechanics. In the case of light, it was assumed to be a wave in the classical world. A photon, however, may also strike a target in which case it does not act like a wave.

We consider these ideas because we ultimately would like to know why one should use $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ (where $\exp(ipx)$ is the free particle wavefunction) to obtain $P(x) = \text{constant}$, in order to describe a density.

How Does $\exp(ipx)$ Arise?

We have suggested in previous notes that $\exp(ipx)$ ultimately arises from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ ((1))

This is a completely classical result.

As a result, $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ yield the same A values for $n = \text{integer}$. This suggests intervals in space of \hbar/p . If one uses the maximum entropy idea, then one should have a uniform probability in x in each \hbar/p unit. In other words, there is both x resolution and uniform probability in each.

If one argues that there is no way to measure this \hbar/p resolution in a system, then we argue that one essentially has a uniform x distribution in each \hbar/p and so in all x . This in turn leads to $P(x) = \text{constant}$ and is consistent with $x = vt$. $P(x)$ is usually called the classical spatial density for a free particle, but we argue that this is not the case. We argue that it only holds if one performs certain kinds of measurements on a free particle which do not depend on the resolution \hbar/p .

For instance, a 2-slit is a classical object which may serve as a measurement device. $P(x) = \text{constant}$ does not predict measurements using a 2-slit, but these are perfectly fine classical measurements. It seems that this special kind of measurement (2-slit) is based on resolution, i.e. a probability for interaction with each slit linked with $\exp(ipx)$.

In the above discussion, we only noted that special relativity yields \hbar/p units with uniform probability if one invokes maximum entropy. The form $\exp(ipx)$ arises if one insists on:

$$P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((2))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of ((2)) which neither grows nor shrinks indefinitely. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is a complex number and so is not a physical observable or based on a usual physical count used in determining a probability for heads/tails or a die toss. Even if one ignores the usual $P(x)dx = dx/L$ because a classical particle spends equal dt times in each constant dx based on $x = vt$, one needs to account for the physical uniform x distribution in each \hbar/p unit. $\exp(ipx)$ must thus map into a uniform distribution in each \hbar/p region. Thus:

$$\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

may be used to show that one indeed has a measurable uniform x distribution in each \hbar/p region. This again suggests a hit-like measurement which does not involve resolution i.e. not a 2-slit measurement.

One may note that in ((3)) all information about p and the \hbar/p pockets is lost. This is because no interaction based on this \hbar/p resolution exists in free space. This, however, is not always the case as the infinite square well potential (or any $V(x)$) shows.

First, however, we wish to note that the maximum entropy assumption leading to a uniform x -probability in each \hbar/p region is consistent with $x=vt$ in each region. Thus, overall the particle moving with $x=vt$ is not inconsistent with $\exp(ipx)$. It seems that it is just the case that $x=vt$ loses the physical reality of \hbar/p resolution units. If there is no way to measure these, as in free space with no n -slits etc., $x=vt$ is perfectly fine. The particle may simply strike a target after traveling according to $x=vt$, even if it is a quantum particle.

The Infinite Square Well

The infinite square well seems like a classical problem, but is actually a quantum one because it involves the resolution length \hbar/p . Like with a classical particle, there can be no probability (or particle) outside the wall boundaries. In classical physics, this always happens at classical turning points, but in quantum mechanics, only with an infinite well. In other words, the infinite well, and other $V(x)$ potentials, involve the resolution lengths \hbar/p .

In the case of the infinite well, one has $\exp(ipave x)$ and $\exp(-ipave x)$. One must take a linear combination and it must be 0 at $x=0$ and $x=L$. As a result, $\hbar/pave$ is critical to the solution. The solution is: $C\sin(pave x)$ where $pave=n*3.14/L$.

$C \sin(pave x)$ is a real number, so why does it not represent a physical observable. First of all, it is negative, but secondly it is constructed of $\exp(ipx)$ s which are not linked directly with a physical measurement. One must use $W^*(x)W(x)$ to try to remove the \hbar/p units as much as possible.

In the case of an interaction which involves resolution, as in the infinite well, the interaction involving resolution is as classical as one which does not. In other words, a 2-slit interaction is a classical interaction, it just must be described by $\exp(ipx)$ which follows mainly from special relativity. It is just that $x=vt$ cannot predict what happens during such an interaction, in other words, Newtonian mechanics is incomplete as we have argued in previous notes.

$\exp(ipx)$ can make predictions for resolution-based interactions, but does not represent a physical observable or count and so once the overall $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx) = W(x)$ is found, one must use $W^*(x)W(x)$ to find the spatial distribution. One may see that if an interaction occurs which involves resolution of \hbar/p 's, then this resolution does not disappear from $W^*(x)W(x)$ as is seen in the n -slit case or the bound $V(x)$ case. This crest pattern, even in the so-called classical probability $W^*(x)W(x)$ manifests the physical \hbar/p resolutions present. These are real, but just not contained in $x=vt$. $x=vt$ maps to the uniform x -distribution in each \hbar/p unit, but completely ignores the existence of units, which are linked to resolution interactions. Thus, $x=vt$ cannot predict spatial density in the case of resolution related interactions.

This then begs the question: How does one know if a resolution based interaction occurs or not?

In general, it seems that $V(x)$ interactions do involve \hbar/p . Thus, for an infinite well potential, even in the energy level \rightarrow infinite limit, one may use the quantum $\exp(ipave x) + \exp(-ipave x)$ approach and consider the result to be correct.

If on the other hand, one argues that one has a ruler with less resolution than \hbar/p and one can only perform a hit measurement which does not depend on \hbar/p region $=dx$, then an $x=vt$ description is an approximation to the problem and describes classical physics, we argue.

Resolution and Non-Resolution Determining Interactions

We have argued that $\exp(ipx)$ ultimately arises from $A = -Et + px$ (along with $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P((p_1+p_2)x)$). There is nothing nonclassical about this except that one is making use of extra information in special relativity, namely the degeneracy of A for $x = x_0 + n\hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n\hbar/E$, which is usually ignored. It is ignored because one usually does not deal with interactions which involve \hbar/p resolution. The reason for this seems to be that 2-slit measurements, which are completely classical, would involve slits which are too close together in the macroscopic world and so were not observed. This does not mean that there is anything nonclassical about a 2-slit apparatus with the two slits very close to each other. If such resolution based interactions are not seen, then it is assumed that they do not exist experimentally and only results linked to measurements which commonly occur are included in a theory, e.g. Newtonian mechanics.

In Newtonian mechanics, one also has bound states in a potential $V(x)$, but again even though $V(x)$ does involve \hbar/p resolutions in interactions, these are again not seen and one opts for the simpler acceleration picture in dx units which are much larger than \hbar/p 's involved.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $x=vt$ is linked to $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length in classical physics. We suggest that special relativity allows for degeneracies in $A = -Et + px$, so $x = x_0 + n\hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n\hbar/E$ suggests resolutions in space and time. In the macroscopic world, resolution based interactions are not seen because \hbar/p is too small for a particle. They are, however, seen for light. In other words, an n -slit measurement is completely classical, it is just not practical because of the tiny lengths involved for particles.

We note that $x=vt$ suggests a uniform x distribution in all of space, while a maximum entropy approach to the \hbar/p spatial units suggests a uniform x -distribution only in each \hbar/p . If one has no way of measuring the \hbar/p resolutions, then one has $x=vt$ and a uniform distribution throughout space both classical and quantum mechanically, i.e. consider a quantum particle traveling through space and hitting a target.

If on the other hand, there is a resolution based interaction, such as a 2-slit apparatus, then one must use the \hbar/p resolution approach. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ appears as a solution of $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P((p_1+p_2)x)$ ((B)). $\exp(ipx)$, however, is a complex number and does not express a real count as in usual classical probabilities. It must, however, map to the uniform x -distribution contained in each \hbar/p , hence $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$. This idea then is applied to $W(x) = \sum a(p)\exp(ipx)$, i.e. $W^*(x)W(x)$, but $W(x)$ arises from resolution based interactions with a potential $V(x)$ as in a bound case.

In Newtonian mechanics, one assumes that $V(x)$ does not involve any resolutions because these cannot be seen. Thus, one has $dx = v(x)dt(x)$ in each fixed dx unit. This, we argue, is an

approximation of what really happens, i.e what is described by $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from special relativity (which is a classical theory) together with ((B)) which is also a completely classical notion.